

Using Torque and RPM loss to estimate the presence of icing clouds with UAVs

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Introduction

- Drones struggle to fly in icing and cloudy conditions.
- Focus:** monitoring rotational speed (RPM) and torque loss when traversing cloud and icing conditions.
- Alternative methods are too expensive or not reliable to be used in UAV applications
- Objective:** to precisely measure the impact of cloud and icing environments on drone performance
- Method:** Collecting data using onboard computers and quantifying using the Han-Palacios Correlation
- Outcome:** Better understanding of cloud's water content and mean volume diameter of droplets.

Figure 1: Propeller icing diagram

Goals/Methods

- The primary goal of this research:
- to enhance the reliability and safety of UAVs
 - mainly those in challenging cloud and icing conditions.
 - Using a pixhawk flight controller
 - The data will be collected through the onboard Odroid computer.
 - Han-Palacios correlation will be used to process the data.

Figure 2: Pixhawk flight controller

Expected outcomes

- Previous studies were on single rotor aircraft
- Adjusting some values for UAVs, we should achieve a dataset of this type:

Figure 3: Expected Data values for UAV icing

Learnings

- Off the Shelf LiDAR is a cheap and effective solution to range detection and spatial imaging.
- however, falls severely short when imaging clouds due to its inability to resolve small droplets.
- Other solutions (including image processing systems) are too expensive or fragile to be put on UAVs.

Figure 4: LiDAR imaging diagram

Conclusion and Future Research

- Future research will focus on
- refining these measurements under varying environmental conditions
 - developing robust algorithms for real-time data processing.
 - exploring solutions for mitigating icing effects on drones, such as de-icing systems or optimized flight paths.

Figure 5: Three mission critical attributes plotted for expected results

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